

Enhancing the Marine Virtual Laboratory

Enhancing the Marine Virtual Laboratory (MARVL) to support the national ocean modelling system.

The MARVL will be modified to provide access to new datasets, modelling and services that maximise the value of observation sets through data assimilation, technically known as reanalysis. The MARVL is also critical to supporting the Australian National Shelf-seas Reanalysis.

Start date

20 December 2017

Expected completion date

30 June 2019

Investment by ARDC

\$625,000

Co-investment partners

- [University of Tasmania](#)
- [Bureau of Meteorology Science for Services and Community Forecasts Programs \(BoM\)](#)
- [CSIRO Oceans & Atmosphere Coastal Modelling Team \(CSIRO\)](#)
- [National Computational Infrastructure \(NCI\)](#)
- [South Australia Research and Development Institute \(SARDI\)](#)
- [Tasmanian Partnership for Advanced Computing \(TPAC\)](#)
- [University of New South Wales \(UNSW\)](#)
- [University of Western Australia \(UWA\)](#)
- [MetOcean Solutions Ltd NZ \(MOS\)](#)
- [Integrated Marine Observing System \(IMOS\)](#)

Lead node

UNIVERSITY of TASMANIA

1. Datasets

Acquire and assemble the datasets crucial to underpinning the shelf-seas reanalysis. Assembly of relevant observation collections and data sets related to ocean, atmosphere, tidal and bathymetry. Acquiring and assembling the initial dataset for coastal discharge.

2. Superobs

Develop service for preparing "model ready" observations (superobs) for use in the intended data assimilation schemes (Ensemble Kalman Filter, Ensemble Optimal Interpolation or ROMS-4DVAR)

3. Test cases

Develop test cases by modelling teams (BoM, CSIRO, SARDI, UNSW, UWA) demonstrating the utility of the new services. The test cases are to be: Great Barrier Reef (GBR) -

Core features

Datasets

Extensive collection of datasets all in one place Datasets include atmospheric reanalyses, ocean reanalyses, bathymetry, tidal forcing, and new information relating to freshwater discharge at the coast.

Services

Complete set of services required to get your "model ready" data The services necessary to structure initial and forcing conditions for model simulations, and services for preparing 'model ready' observations for use in the intended data assimilation schemes.

Who is this project for?

- marine researchers (national and international)
- industry (e.g. fisheries, aquaculture, offshore energy)
- marine managers
- weather forecasters

What does this project enable?

This project provides the necessary data to run models and to construct services to enable model ingestion of observational data into data assimilation schemes that are essential for conducting reanalysis as required by the Australian National Shelf-seas Reanalysis (ANSR).

Handy resources

Access the [MARVL portal](#)
Access forcing datasets from the [NCI THREDDS catalogue](#)

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